

Original article

Epidemiology and outcome of trauma patients admitted into the Intensive Care Unit of Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University Teaching Hospital, Bauchi: a 5-year retrospective review

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Abstract

Background: Trauma remains a major cause of morbidity and mortality worldwide, disproportionately afflicting young and economically productive individuals. This study aimed to describe the epidemiology and outcomes of trauma patients admitted to the ICU of Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University Teaching Hospital (ATBUTH), Bauchi. **Materials and Methods:** This was a retrospective descriptive study conducted using ICU admission and discharge records from January 2021 to December 2025. Sociodemographic data, source of admission, type and cause of injury, number of systems involved, length of ICU stay, and outcomes were extracted using a structured Google form. Data were analysed using descriptive statistics and presented in tables and figures. **Results:** Eighty-one trauma patients with complete data were analysed, representing 11.4% of total ICU admissions during the study period. Males accounted for 85.2%, with the highest incidence among those aged 15–29 years (34.6%). Road traffic crashes were the leading cause of injury (55.6%), and craniofacial injuries were most common (49.4%). Most patients had single-system injuries (87.7%) and short ICU stays of ≤ 7 days (88.1%). Admissions predominantly originated from the trauma centre and operating theatre (38.3% each). The mortality proportion was 45.7%. **Conclusion:** Trauma ICU admissions at ATBUTH Bauchi predominantly involve young males injured in road traffic crashes, with a high mortality proportion. Strengthening trauma systems, early intervention, and critical care capacity may improve outcomes.

Keywords: Intensive Care Unit, Road Traffic Crashes, Trauma.

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Introduction

Trauma, defined as any physical injury resulting from external force or violence that disrupts normal anatomy and physiology, represents a major source of morbidity and mortality globally.¹⁻³ Based on its mechanism, trauma is categorised broadly into blunt, penetrating, and deceleration injuries, with each category having distinct injury patterns and clinical challenges.¹ Polytrauma denotes multiple concurrent injuries involving more than one body system, often assessed using standardised scores such as the Injury Severity Score (ISS) to quantify injury severity and prognostic risk.^{1,2,4,5}

Trauma disproportionately affects the younger and economically productive population, contributing substantially to disability and lost productivity worldwide.^{4,6-11} According to global epidemiological data, trauma remains one of the leading causes of death among individuals under 40 years of age and ranks high in global disability-adjusted life years (DALYs).^{7,9} The intensive care unit (ICU) serves as the critical care nexus where severely injured trauma patients undergo resuscitation, organ support, and monitoring.

In Nigeria, trauma accounts for a significant proportion of ICU admissions. A retrospective review of general ICUs in Nigeria found that trauma accounted for 25.1-68% of total admissions.⁷⁻⁹, with a male predominance and a young median age⁷⁻⁹; this parallels what is found globally^{2-4,6,10,11}. Burns and road traffic crashes (RTCs) were the most common causes of trauma.⁷⁻⁹, and mortality among these patients approached 43-48.7%.^{7,8} This can be explained by the absence of a centralised trauma registry and an ambulance and trauma response system in the country.⁵ Study in Ethiopia by Messelu et al¹¹ found violence (58.9%) to be the commonest cause of trauma among patients admitted into the ICU.

Patients with the highest mortality in the developing countries were found to have been involved in burns or RTC.^{7-9,11}

In contrast to low- and middle-income countries (LMICs), trauma ICUs in high-income settings benefit from integrated trauma systems, regionalised care, and extensive trauma registries.^{2-4,6,10} Cohort analyses report that trauma patients account for 13-33.8% of ICU admissions.^{2,3} Males predominate, with a male:female ratio of 1:3.^{3,4,6} A lower mortality rate, between 20.6% and 28.2%, was reported in the developed world.^{6,10}, which can easily be explained by more advanced care and presence of standardised trauma response and ambulance services, and the leading causes of death were found to be RTC and blunt injury^{2-4,6,10}

Trauma is a major cause of ICU admission and mortality in Nigeria, yet locally contextualised data remain limited. Understanding the epidemiology, injury patterns, and outcomes of trauma patients in the ICU at Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University Teaching Hospital, Bauchi, will provide evidence to guide resource allocation, improve trauma care strategies, and strengthen critical care services.

The study will provide baseline data on trauma burden and outcomes in the ICU at Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University Teaching Hospital, Bauchi. Findings will support evidence-based trauma management, guide policy development, improve resource planning, and contribute to national data on trauma care in Nigeria.

Aim

To evaluate the epidemiology and clinical outcomes of trauma patients admitted to the ICU of Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University Teaching Hospital, Bauchi.

Objectives:

1. Determine the demographic characteristics of trauma patients admitted to the ICU.
2. Identify the common causes and types of trauma.
3. Determine the sources of ICU admission.
4. Evaluate injury patterns, ICU length of stay, and patient outcomes.

Materials and Methods

Study Setting

The hospital's trauma centre is a 26-bed unit with an HDU, a side laboratory, a blood bank, a radiography unit, and an operating theatre. It is manned by casualty officers and other specialist teams on call from every unit in the hospital; emergency nurses work together with the team of doctors via a shift duty roster.

Patients reviewed in the trauma centre by a casualty officer were handed over to the respective specialist team; upon review, they were transferred to various wards within the hospital. Those who required ICU admission were reviewed by the ICU team on call and those with reversible life-threatening organ dysfunction were admitted.

The hospital's general intensive care unit (ICU) has six beds. Among other things, it has an ultrasound scanner, mechanical ventilators, and advanced multiparameter monitors.

Patients admitted to the ICU are managed by the ICU team (physician, anaesthetist, critical care nurses) in addition to the primary managing team, which is the referring team.

Data for this retrospective study were obtained by reviewing the ICU admission and discharge register of ATBUTH, Bauchi, from January 2021 to December 2025.

All patients admitted following trauma were identified, and information such as sociodemographic characteristics, source of admission, admitting diagnosis, and outcome was

extracted; this information was collated using a Google form after obtaining ethical clearance from the hospital ethics committee (ATBUTH (REC) assigned number 008/2026).

Inclusion criteria involved all patients whose complete information as required by the Google form can be obtained from the register (name, age, sex, source of admission, month of admission, date of admission, date of discharge, primary managing team, admitting diagnosis and outcome)

Exclusion criteria involved any missing component among the inclusion criteria.

Data was analysed with Microsoft Excel 2024 using descriptive statistical tools, and the presentation includes tables and charts.

Results

Participant Characteristics

A total of 86 trauma patients were admitted between January 2021 and December 2025; however, only 81 patients had complete data for recruitment into the study, which gives a retrieval rate (patients with complete data) of 94%. Total ICU admissions during the same period were 711, and trauma patients constituted 81 of them, or 11.4% of total ICU admissions.

The distribution of the patients by age and sex, as shown in Table 1, revealed that the highest age range was 15-29 years (34.6%) followed by 30-34 years (27.2%). This shows that trauma commonly occurred in the young age group; children less than 1 year account for 16%, while elderly above 65 years account for 6.2%.

Table 1: Age and Sex Distribution of Trauma Patients

Age category (yrs)	Frequency	Percentage
0-14	13	16.0
15-29	28	34.6
30-44	22	27.2
45-64	13	16.0
>65	5	6.2
Total	81	100

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	69	85.2
Female	12	14.8
Total	81	100

The majority of the patients were found to be male, 85.2%, and females account for 14.8% of the trauma patients. This shows males are more involved in trauma than women, which can easily be explained

by more involvement in risky activities by male subjects.

We found that the majority of the trauma occurs during the dry season in the state (month of May) 12.3% while the least occurs during the rainy season (month of August), 3.7%. This is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Distribution of Trauma Patients by Month of Admission

Neurosurgical patients constitute 55.6% of the trauma cases; ENT and plastic surgery each constitute 16%; and general surgery and orthopaedics make up 6.2% of the trauma cases during the study period (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Distribution of trauma patients by Managing team

Figure 3 shows that the theatre and trauma centre accounted for 38.3% of the study population's

source of admission, while 23.5% of patients were referred from various hospital wards.

Figure 3: Distribution by Source of admission for trauma patients

This aligns with the presentation of trauma patients with hemodynamic instability, or requiring damage control surgery as part of resuscitation measures.

Table II shows the distribution of patients by site of injury, type of injury, number of systems involved, and length of ICU stay.

Craniofacial injuries top the list at 49.4% (40 cases), followed by soft tissue injuries (27.2%, 22 cases) and burns (16%, 13 cases); fractures are the least common (7.4%, 6 cases).

Road traffic crashes account for over half (55.6%, 45 cases), with domestic accidents accounting for 28.4% (23 cases), while violence is lowest at 16% (13 cases).

Most patients (87.7%, 71 cases) had single-system injuries, while multiple systems were involved in just 12.3% (10 cases).

Short stays prevail: 88.1% (72 cases) lasted 0-7 days, with only 7.4% (6 cases) at 8-14 days, 2.5% (2 cases) at 15-21 days, and 1.2% (1 case) over 21 days. A high short-stay rate indicates efficient stabilisation or high acuity, with rapid outcomes (e.g., discharge or mortality).

This aligns with characteristics of trauma, where most patients do well after early resuscitation and stabilisation, while fatal cases die immediately.

Discussion

The study revealed that ICU trauma bed occupancy is 11.4%, which is similar to 29.66% reported by HY Embu et al.⁷, and 25.1% by KE Amaefule et al.⁹ in the northern part of the country. It is lower than the

68% obtained by Olajumoke et al.⁸ in the southern part of the country. This likely reflects a composite of socioeconomic and structural barriers. High out-of-pocket costs for critical care and greater wealth disparity often lead to financial triage, where families opt out of intensive care.

Table 2: Distribution of trauma patients by site of injury, cause of injury, number of systems involved and length of ICU stay

Site of injury	Frequency	Percentage
Burns	13	16.0
Craniofacial	40	49.4
Fractures	6	7.4
Soft tissue injuries	22	27.2
Total	81	100

Cause of injury

Cause of injury	Frequency	Percentage
Domestic accidents	23	28.4
Road traffic crash	45	55.6
Violence (assault, communal clash, robbery)	13	16.0
Total	81	100

Number of systems involved

Number of systems involved	Frequency	Percentage
Single	71	87.7
Multiple	10	12.3
Total	81	100

Length of ICU stay (days)

Length of ICU stay (days)	Frequency	Percentage
0-7	72	88.1
8-14	6	7.4
15-21	2	2.5
>21	1	1.2
Total	81	100

Considering the various aetiologies of trauma, young individuals are commonly involved in the activities leading to trauma, our study finds that young individuals constitute the majority of our trauma admissions in the ICU, with age ranges 15-29 years (34.6%), and 30-44 years (27.2%) being the highest percentages, this is similar to what other people reported (age range of 15-45 years^{8,9,11}) as the

most commonly involved in trauma, and HY Embu et al.⁷ reported a median age of 26.9±16.4 years.

Male patients account for 85.2% of trauma admissions based on our study, which is similar to what is obtained globally by various studies, with male patients accounting for 75-80% of trauma ICU admissions.^{6-9,11-13} This male predominance likely reflects greater engagement in high-risk activities and occupations.

The 38.3% of admissions originating from the trauma centre is in agreement with findings from Nigerian tertiary hospitals, where trauma continues to be a predominant factor in emergency admissions and the utilisation of intensive care resources. Olajumoke et al.⁸ illustrated that the majority of trauma patients (74.1%) at their facility stemmed from the Accident and Emergency unit, predominantly due to road traffic accidents and other significant trauma incidents.

Equally significant is the considerable percentage of admissions from the operating theatre (38.3%), indicating that a substantial number of patients required vigilant postoperative monitoring or enhanced organ support following surgical interventions. This observation is consistent with findings reported by HY Embu et al.⁷ and Amaefulu et al.⁹ Such patients typically require intensive monitoring due to factors such as hemodynamic instability, challenges in pain management, or existing comorbid conditions.

The 23.5% referral rate from hospital wards indicates ongoing clinical deterioration among inpatients initially managed outside critical care settings. Comparable ward-to-ICU referral patterns have been documented in other Nigerian studies and are frequently attributed to delayed identification of clinical decline, limited ward monitoring capabilities, and shortages of adequately trained personnel. This finding accentuates the urgent need for enhanced early warning systems, staff education, and rapid response protocols to ensure timely escalation of care.

This study identified Neurosurgical patients as the primary trauma cohorts (55.6%), a finding that stands in stark contrast to the data from Gun et al.⁴ A study on retrospective analysis of trauma patients, where general surgical patients predominate, 29.1%. This discrepancy highlights the unique trauma signature of our environment. The high prevalence of neurotrauma in our centre likely reflects the high incidence of motorcycle-related crashes and suboptimal use of personal protective equipment, such as helmets. Furthermore, the relative scarcity of general

surgical trauma compared to Western cohorts may be influenced by high prehospital mortality rates for truncal haemorrhage, whereas patients with traumatic brain injuries are more likely to survive the initial transit to reach definitive neurosurgical care.

Trauma can have varying aetiologies from RTC, Burns, domestic accidents, and violence. In this study, 55.6% of the trauma was a result of RTC. This can be explained by the fact that Bauchi State has a large highway network, which serves as the major link between other northeastern states and the north-central part of the country. And it aligns with the findings of other studies within and outside the country, where they reported RTC as the leading cause of trauma admission into the ICU in 60.1-74.1% of their study population.^{2,4,6,8,9,12} However, a study conducted by HY Embu et al.⁷ In JUTH, reported burns were the commonest cause of trauma admission into the ICU, constituting 40.40% of the study population, while RTC was second with 38.38%. While Messelu et al.¹¹ In a study in a terror-ravaged community, reported violence (58.9%) was the commonest cause of trauma admission in their ICU.

Trauma patients may have single or multiple systems involved (based on body region), but in the majority of cases, the patients may have some degree of head injury, as the head and neck are the commonly affected sites based on analysis of studies, which found that the head and neck are involved in 36-95.9%^{7-9,11,12} of the study population. In this study, we observe that the craniofacial region is involved in 49.4% of the population, and 12.3% of our study population have more than one system involved. A study by Gun et al.⁴ In a research and training hospital intensive care unit in Turkey, long bone fractures were reported as the commonest site involved in trauma among 54.7% of the patients. This can be due to having a speciality dedicated ICU in the developed world.

Patients may stay in ICU for varying duration, depending on the nature of their condition and other complications that may arise during their stay, however trauma patients usually have short duration because the condition improve significantly within the first week when the metabolic response to trauma is subsiding, in our study we found that 88.9% of our study population stay ≤7 days which is similar to what is reported by HY Embu et al.⁷ (59.09%), KE Amaefule et al.⁹ (75%). While Chalya et al.¹² reported 64.9% to stay ≤3 days, and Olajumoke et al.⁸ reported that 66% of patients stayed 7-14 days. This is still in keeping with the

time taken for the resolution of metabolic response to trauma.

Trauma patients may have surgery during their stay in ICU or they can undergo the surgery even before admission into the ICU, as this can serve as damage control resuscitation or definitive surgery which usually lead to a lot of stress response with haemodynamic instability, our studies found out 45.7% of our patients undergo surgery at one point or the other during their stay, a study in turkey training and research hospital by Gun et al.⁴ reported 81.4% of their patients had undergone surgical intervention.

The majority of our patients (54.3%) were successfully managed and subsequently discharged to various hospital wards. This gives a mortality of 45.7%, which is similar to the results of other studies in the country by HY Embu et al.⁷ (48.74%) and Olajumoke et al.⁸ (43%).

However, the results from developed countries reported lower percentages by Gun et al.⁴ (25.6%), and Agorogianni et al.¹³ (21.5%). Because developed countries have established rapid-response and ambulance systems with more equipment and personnel for advanced critical care, they may be able to salvage patients who would likely not survive in developing countries.

Strengths of the Study

1. Provides locally relevant data on trauma epidemiology and ICU outcomes in Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University Teaching Hospital, Bauchi, where such data are scarce.
2. Covers five years, allowing better observation of patterns and trends in trauma admissions.
3. Uses real ICU records, reflecting actual clinical practice and outcomes.
4. Offers baseline data that can guide trauma care planning and resource allocation.

Limitations of the Study

1. Retrospective design depends on the accuracy and completeness of medical records.
2. Single-centre study limits generalisability to other hospitals or regions.
3. Small sample size of trauma ICU admissions may affect statistical power.
4. Some clinical variables (e.g., injury severity scores or prehospital care data) were unavailable or incompletely documented.
5. Lack of injury severity scoring

Conclusion:

Trauma patients make up a 11.4% of ICU admissions, and mortality is a little below 50%. A structured transport system, along with more equipment and personnel in the critical care unit, will improve morbidity and mortality in this group of patients. Public education and enforcement of road safety rules will help reduce the occurrence of RTC, which is a major cause of trauma.

Authors contribution

Aliyu Bashir Adamu- Design and conception of the work, analysis and interpretation of data.

Ibrahim Salim Adullahi, Abubakar M. Ballah, Rabi Mohammed Bashir, Nasir Mohammed Usman, Aliyu Abdullahi Musa- proofreading and

reviewing it critically for important intellectual content. Sani Sulaiman Bara, Bashiru Isah Ibrahim, Yusuf Raiyanu Jasawa, Fatima Mohammed Mustapha, Anas Hamza Abubakar, Hassana Dauda Gololo, Maryam Yunusa, Abdulhakim Sani Aliyu- contribution to the design of the work and data collection.

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